

Smile Traits And Designing In Orthodontics : A Review

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Abstract

It is important for orthodontists to make every effort to develop a harmonious balance that will produce the most attractive smile possible for each patient treated. A smile usually translates a common man emotional

intelligence and expresses his feeling in a unique fashion Thus, he seeks the orthodontist to improve the esthetics and especially the smile. The success of smile design is determined by the patient's profile and the orthodontist's esthetic goals and skill so as to re-establish patients' expectations. This article enlightens the overview few characteristics for a balanced smile.

Keywords : Balanced smile, smile arc, smile design

Introduction

Patients expectation from orthodontic treatment has evolved over the years to include smile esthetics as an important compound.^[1] Smile plays an important role in facial expression and appearance, studies with photographs denote that higher intellectual and social abilities were attributed to individuals with esthetic smile.^[2] These concepts of smile esthetics are not new but are too often overlooked in orthodontic treatment planning.^[3] Creating an esthetic smile requires an understanding of the principle that manage the balance between teeth and soft tissues^[4] Although ideal occlusion should be the primary functional goal of orthodontics, the esthetic result is also critical for patient satisfaction and therefore necessary to the overall treatment objectives. Hence, orthodontic treatment must incorporate various esthetic elements to achieve desirable results. The most important esthetic goal in orthodontics is to achieve a balanced smile which can be best described as an appropriate positioning of teeth and gingival scaffold within the dynamic display zone; hence, it is reasonable to analyze smile as important criteria for diagnosis and orthodontic treatment planning. Currently, a pleasant smile, mainly influenced by the beauty monetary standard imposed by the media, is characterized by the presence of perfectly aligned and leveled dentition in the dental arch.^[5] Smile analysis is part of a seventh cranial

nerve analysis and allows dentists to recognize positive and negative elements in each patient's smile. Depending on the type of malocclusion, facial shape of the patient and mechanics adopted, orthodontic intervention can prove either beneficial or harmful to smile esthetics. Thus, it is reasonable to regard smile analysis as an important tool for diagnosis and orthodontic treatment planning.^[6]

Historical AspectsThe study of frontal facial form dates back to the Egyptians, who depicted ideal facial esthetics as the golden proportion. This concept has been described extensively in classical art and orthodontic literature. Edward Angle emphasis on occlusion led him to teach that optimal facial esthetics always coincided with ideal occlusion and that esthetics could essentially be disregarded because it took care of itself. Furthermore, the early concepts of esthetics revolved largely around the patient's profile, and it was believed that, once the "ideal" tooth-jaw positions were achieved, then the soft tissues would fall in line. This focus on the profile was because the lateral cephalogram has long been the lynchpin of orthodontic treatment planning.^[7]

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Anatomy of Smile

The upper and lower lips frame the display zone of the smile. Within this framework, the components of the smile are the teeth and the gingival scaffold. The soft-tissue determinants of the display zone are lip thickness, intercommissure width, interlabial gap, smile index (width/height), and gingival architecture.

Although the commissures of the lips form the lateral borders of the smile, the eye can perceive inner and outer commissures, as delineated by the innermost and outermost confluences, respectively, of the vermilion of the lips at the corners of the mouth. The inner commissure is formed by the mucosa overlying the buccinator muscle where it inserts with the orbicularis oris muscle fibers at the modiolus.

Smile Design

It must be understood that there is no universal "ideal" smile. The most important esthetic goal in orthodontics is to achieve a "balanced" smile,^[8] which can best be described as an appropriate positioning of the teeth and gingival scaffold within the dynamic display zone. As mentioned above, this includes lateral, vertical, and anteroposterior aspects, as well as the cant of the maxillary anterior transverse occlusal plane and the sagittal cant of the maxillary occlusal plane. Smile design and mechanotherapy must be built around this esthetic plane of occlusion, which is often different from the natural plane of occlusion.^[9]

Golden Proportions

The definition of the laws of harmony and beauty were a constant preoccupation with the ancient Greeks. The divine proportion has been attributed to Pythagoras, and its esthetic values were stressed by Luca Pacioli in his book *Divine Proportione* illustrated by Da Vinci. The application of the divine proportion to dentistry was attributed to Lombardi and then developed by Levin using calipers that open at a constant divine proportion between the larger and smaller parts, Levin observed that in esthetically pleasing dentitions viewed from the front the width of the central incisors in the golden proportion to the lateral incisor which is in golden proportion to the anterior part of the canine. He also demonstrated that the width of the negative space is in golden proportion to one-half of the width of the anterior segment. The buccal corridor is said to be in golden proportion to the anterior smile. It is a key factor in the harmony of a smile. From these observations, he developed a grid to test the validity of this statement, in the grid the incisors are quoted within a large range of width. The use of this grid helps the dentist determine what is esthetically wrong with the anterior proportional dentition.

Smile Classification

Smiles are classified as the social smile and the enjoyment smile. The social smile is a voluntary, static facial expression, unstrained. Due to moderate muscular contraction of the lip elevator muscles the lips part, and the teeth and sometimes the gingival scaffold are displayed^[10]. The enjoyment smile is involuntary. It results from maximal contraction of the upper lip elevator and lower lip depressor muscles causing full

expansion of the lips, with maximum anterior tooth and gingival display. A smile can also be classified into three types of smile depending on the exposure of tooth and gingival.^[11] Muscles Anatomy of Smile

Nasolabial fold is the keystone of the smiling mechanism and five muscles effectively control smile. The muscles of expression are located around the mouth, they are the depressor anguli oris, the risorius, the zygomaticus major, the zygomaticus minor, and the levator labii superioris. All these muscles, specifically the zygomaticus muscles are involved with smiling; they pull the orbicularis oris upward. These muscles are innervated by the various branches of the facial nerve. Smile is formed in two stages. In the first stage, the levator muscles contract and raise the upper lip to nasolabial fold. In the second stage, the levator labii superioris, zygomaticus major, and buccinator muscles raise the lips even more superiorly. The final stage is often characterized by the appearance of squinting. It represents the contraction of the periocular musculature to support maximum upper-lip elevation through the fold.^[12]

Components of Smile

The principles of smile design require an integration of esthetic concepts that harmonize facial esthetics with the dental facial composition and the dental composition.^[13] Various components of a balanced smile are lip line, buccal corridor, smile arc, upper-lip curvature, smile symmetry, frontal occlusal plane, dental components, and gingival components.

Lip line

The lip line is the amount of vertical tooth exposure in smiling.^[14,15] The amount of in smiling tooth exposure depends on the following six factors. Upper lip length, lip elevation, vertical maxillary height, crown height, vertical dental height, incisor inclination and are arbitrarily classified as low lip line, middle lip line, or high lip line.^[16] An average lip line exposes the maxillary teeth and only the interdental papillae. A high lip line exposes the teeth in full display as well as gingival tissues above the gingival margins. A low lip line displays no gingival tissues when smiling. In most cases, the lip line is acceptable if it is within a range of 2 mm apical to the height of the gingiva on the maxillary centrals.

Buccal corridor or lateral negative space

The buccal corridor is more commonly referred by orthodontists as lateral negative space. It is defined as the distance between the maxillary posterior teeth (especially the premolars) and the inside of the cheek.^[17] It appears as a black or dark space. In transverse dimension of the smile is also referred to as "transverse dental projection." Fresh and Fischer demonstrated that the presence of buccal corridors added the illusion of a natural dentition, whereas its absence gave the patient an artificial appearance. The orthodontist's eye for beauty is an important factor in creating appropriately sized buccal corridors. In smiling, the width of the mouth increases by as much as 30%, therefore, an excessive transverse lip extension in smiling

would produce a wider buccal corridor.^[18] The buccal corridor is influenced by dental structures and soft tissue structures rather than underlying skeletal structures.

Smile arc

The smile arc is the relationship between a hypothetical curve drawn along the edges of the maxillary anterior teeth and the inner contour of the lower lip in the posed smile. The smile arc is defined as the relationship of the contour of the incisal edges of the maxillary anterior teeth relative to the curvature of lower lip during a social smile. On the basis of this relationship, smile lines are of three types: Consonant smile arc, Straight smile arc, and Reverse smile arc. Since the smile arc depends on occlusal plane inclination and second order crown angulations in the upper anterior teeth, there are some limitations to the achievement of this ideal smile arc on every patient. A reasonable objective is to prevent a flat or reverse smile arc and to obtain some degree of curvature that resembles, one found in the lower lip.^[19]

High smile	The smile in which complete cervicoincisal length of the maxillary incisors and the band of gingiva is visible is called as high smile
Average smile	The smile in which 75%-100% of the maxillary incisors is visible is called as average smile
Low smile	In this type of smile about less than 75%, of maxillary incisor is only visible
Gummy smile	There can also be a category of excess gingival exposure called as gummy smile. This anatomical feature is defined by peck and peck as gingival smile line

Upper-lip curvature

It refers to the curvature of the upper lip formed while smiling, its often observed in the frontal view and evaluated on the curvature from the middle of the vermilion of the upper lip to the lateral commissures. It is mainly directed by an individual's muscular anatomy and dentoskeletal morphology. It is straight when the corner of the mouth and the central position are at the same level, upward when the corner of the mouth is higher than the central position, and downward when the corner of the mouth is lower than the central position.^[20]

Smile symmetry

It is the relative positioning of the corners of the mouth in the vertical plane; it can be assessed by the parallelism of the commissural and pupillary lines.^[21] An esthetic smile harmony forms from the teeth, the gingival scaffold, and the lip framework. Smile symmetry is one of the miniesthetic components of dentofacial analyses, and a symmetric smile is considered more attractive, impaired

symmetry in smiles could be due to the presence of a skeletal asymmetry. An assessment of smile symmetry before orthodontic treatment or orthognathic surgery is considered important for evaluating treatment outcomes.^[22,23]

Frontal Occlusal Plane

The frontal occlusal plane is represented by a line running from the tip of the right canine to the tip of the left canine. A transverse cannot can be caused by the differential eruption of the maxillary anterior teeth or a skeletal asymmetry of the mandible.^[24]

Dental Components

Dental components of the smile include the size, shape, color, alignment, and crown angulation (tip) of the teeth; the midline; and arch symmetry.^[25] The dental midline is an important focal point in an esthetic smile. A practical and reliable method of locating the facial midline, which normally coincides with the dental midline, is to use two anatomical landmarks: Nasion and the base of the philtrum, known as the "cupid's bow," in the center of the upper lip. A line drawn between these two landmarks not only locates the facial mid-line but also determines its direction. The parallelism between the maxillary central incisor midline and the facial midline is more important than the coincidence between the dental and facial midlines.

Gingival Components

Esthetic enhancement of smile requires prior quantification of gingival component of smile. The gingival components of the smile are the color, contour, texture, and height of the gingivae. Inflammation, blunted papillae, open gingival embrasures, and uneven gingival margins detract from the esthetic quality of the smile.^[26] Maxillary central incisors and the central papilla, because of their location in the midline and being the most prominent, are first noticeable in appearance.

Hence, visibility of central papilla, adjacent teeth, and gingival display and their association with the smile line are considered to be the key esthetic factors in smile of any individual. The exposure of the teeth during smile varies from person to person; concomitantly amount of gingiva in a smile also varies. To design a smile we need to determine the amount of part to be exposed along with the exposure of the teeth. Framing the teeth, within the confines of the gingival architecture, has a tremendous impact on the esthetics of the smile. A gummy smile is as unesthetic as a patient with a severe recession.

The impact on the beauty of a smile from an uneven gingival contour height can be dramatic, and although the position of the zenith of the gingival tissue seems like a small detail, it can greatly influence the axial inclination and emergence profile of the teeth.^[27,28]

Protecting and Enhancing Smile Arcs

Factors that can make it more difficult to protect existing smile arcs or enhance inadequate smile arcs during treatment include^[29]

- Inappropriate conventional bracket positioning, which typically reduces or flattens the smile arc (and wire plane) during leveling.
- The relative steepness or flatness of the occlusal plane (the flatter the plane, the more difficult it is to manage the smile arc esthetically).
- Incisor proclination, whether preexisting or iatrogenic.
- A particularly broad anterior archform, in which the excessive intercanine span tends to flatten the smile arc.
- Steep upper canine tips and inappropriate canine bracket positioning in relation to the incisors.
- Irregular shapes or size disproportions among the incisors and canines

Effect of Bracket Position on Wire Plane

If a full enamel display with 1-1.5mm of gingival display provides the most esthetically pleasing and youthful smile dimensions, it is important to appreciate the negative effect of leveling-especially upper incisor intrusion in a deep-bite case-on the smile arc. Upper incisor intrusion is only rarely esthetically desirable, even for a Class II, division 2 malocclusion. If the patient has a gummy smile, an esthetic smile arc should be developed by using SAP bracket positioning and temporary anchorage devices or utility aches for intrusion, rather than relying on bracket position.

To develop a pleasing smile arc and positively affect the anterior portion of the upper occlusal plane cant, the maxillary anterior brackets are positioned more gingivally for SAP than in traditional techniques (fig.1).

Fig.1 Bracket placement concepts. A. Traditional. B. Slot at facial axis point. C. SAP positioning. (© Dr. Rungsi Thavarungkul, Bangkok, Thailand.)

The maxillary archwire plane is then parallel to the upper lip; the incisal edges of the upper anterior teeth will follow the lower lip with treatment (fig.2).

Fig. 2 With SAP bracket positioning, maxillary archwire plane is parallel to upper lip; incisal edges of upper anterior teeth will follow lower lip

during treatment. (Case image courtesy of Dr. Tomás Castellanos, Bogotá, Colombia.)

The divergence of the wire from the occlusal cusp tips or incisal edges increases from posterior to anterior (fig.3).

Fig. 3 To develop pleasing smile arc display and positively affect upper occlusal plane cant, maxillary anterior brackets must be positioned more gingivally for SAP than in traditional techniques.

Divergence of wire from cusp tips or incisal edges increases from posterior to anterior. (© Dr. Rungsi Thavarungkul, Bangkok, Thailand.)

The greater the differential from the buccal segments to the anterior segment, the more the wire plane helps increase the maxillary occlusal plane cant in relation to true Frankfort horizontal (NHP). When needed, miniscrews can be utilized as anchorage to intrude the lower anterior teeth, allowing more vertical movement of the upper incisors. Favorable wire planes produced by SAP bracket positions induce extrusion of the upper incisors relative to the upper premolars, resulting in the application of a clockwise moment to the upper anterior teeth from the outset of treatment. When the occlusion is disarticulated with bite turbos and mechanics are supported by very light, short elastics from the first appointment, uprighting of proclined teeth will begin, even on light, round wires. Clinicians report that these techniques can improve upper incisor and gingival display, smile arc, and incisor inclinations as early as the third appointment. Taking “every patient, every appointment” clinical photos is exceptionally helpful in assessing esthetic progress, so that case management can be adjusted accordingly.

When additional retroclination of the incisors is desired, the mechanics can be further supported by inverting the upper anterior brackets 180°, producing active lingual crown torque in the slot with dimensional archwires 9 (fig.4).

Fig. 4 When additional retroclination of anterior teeth is desired, inverting upper anterior brackets 180° provides additional bracket torque, as indicated by circled numbers. (Case image courtesy of Dr. Tomás Castellanos, Bogotá, Colombia.)

Inversion does not alter the tip or in-out geometry of well-designed incisor brackets. Unfortunately, due to a number of common factors—oversize bracket slots, inconsistent slot geometries (as caused by poor manufacturing tolerance control), overly large slot corner radii, variable self-ligating bracket rigidity, and use of excessively small wires— even the highest-quality appliances are not able to deliver consistent expression of their stated torque prescriptions, because torsional play overrides the differences between various prescription values. Moreover, most clinicians do not fill the slot, which further degrades torsional expression.^[30]

The H4* bracket, which features a one-piece self-ligating design, a rigid door, tight manufacturing tolerances, and reduced slot depth (.026" vs. the typical .028"), overcomes some of these challenges and improves efficiency by reducing torsional play. Its use in a well-developed clinical methodology can allow a more purely “straightwire” approach, even when the bracket slot is not filled. The combination of the H4 bracket and progressive “Active Early” case-management strategies goes a long way toward overcoming many of the control problems typically encountered with other passive self-ligating appliance systems.

Effect of Bracket Position on Occlusal Plane

Research has shown that actual clinical torsional play in self-ligating brackets can be as much as two and a half times more than predicted by mathematical models,^[30] making reliable expression of 3rd-order movements problematic. With SAP bracket positioning, the effective prescription of the bracket is reduced relative to the occlusal plane, so that torsional moments for uprighting proclined teeth are engaged early in wire progressions.

It is important to recognize that the maxillary occlusal plane, as viewed in NHP, is a significant contributor to the esthetics of the smile. Obviously, the flatter the plane, the more difficult it is to manage the case esthetically (fig.5).

Fig. 5 With traditional bracket placement, treatment of brachyfacial patient with flat occlusal plane can result in flat smile line. (© Dr. Rungsi Thavarungkul, Bangkok, Thailand.)

Rotating the maxillary occlusal plane clockwise will produce more incisor display and a more convex smile arc. Counterclockwise rotation, which can occur when the upper anterior brackets are placed incisally to the recommended SAP positions, can result in esthetic decline.

In combination with the appropriate use of bite turbos and immediate light, short elastics, SAP bracket positioning helps control the cant of the maxillary occlusal plane from the outset of treatment, offering a wider range of treatment options. Individual bracket positions should be based mainly on

the length of the canines and incisors, as well as the patient's esthetic needs. If the occlusal plane is flat, the gingival bracket divergence should be increased even farther from traditional positioning to enhance enamel and gingival incisor display. In a deep-bite case, the SAP bracket divergence in the upper arch is counteracted by increased overleveling of the lower arch to achieve an optimal overbite. Because it is crucial not to deepen the bite while enhancing the smile arc with individual bracket positioning,^[31] anterior bite turbos should be used to allow eruption of the lower molars.

Effect of Irregular Tooth Shapes and Proportions on Bracket Position

Irregular tooth shapes or size disproportions among the incisors and canines are best addressed through positive or negative coronoplasty (fig.6) prior to bracketing or, at least, early in treatment. Improving the height-width ratio of the “white and pink” tissues is a critical esthetic requirement. Of the three means of crown lengthening, two can be performed by orthodontists: adding composite resin to the incisal edges, or soft-tissue revision with a diode laser. Today's composite resin is easy to apply and durable over the long term. (The third method of crown lengthening is to lift a periodontal flap and recontour bone around the labial aspect of the tooth, which is generally performed by a periodontist.)

The esthetic principle of incisor dominance dictates that the upper central incisor must be the predominant tooth in the esthetic smile.^[30] This means it must display the widest “actual” and “visual” crown and the widest flat surface for light reflection.^[32] It must also be the longest tooth by both actual length and proximity to the idealized lower lip curvature in the posed smile. SAP bracket positioning facilitates incisor dominance because the divergence in bracket progression places the central incisor bracket at the most gingival position of the upper anterior teeth.

Fig. 6. Typical “hanging” canine. B. Idealizing canine contours prior to bonding promotes correct bracket

Conclusion

An attractive, well-balanced smile can be a valuable personal asset. A pleasing smile is important in personal communication and to facial beauty. One's dental and facial appearance is important not only in the role that attractiveness plays to others but also in one's self-concept. Enhancement of facial beauty is one of the primary elective goals of patients seeking dental care. One's dental and facial appearance is important for an attractive and well-balanced smile. Enhancement of facial beauty is one of the primary valuable personal assets for a patient seeking dental care. The goal of orthodontic treatment should be the attainment of the best possible esthetic result, dentally and facially. The smile which

represents the most primitive form and essence of human communicative ability appears early in life in young children. A contributing factor to patient satisfaction at the end of orthodontic treatment is subjective evaluation of facial esthetics. One's dental and facial appearance is important not only in the role that attractiveness plays to others but also in one's self-concept. These concepts of smile esthetics are not new but are too often overlooked in orthodontic treatment planning. The eight components of the smile should be considered not as rigid boundaries, but as artistic guidelines to help orthodontists treat individual patients who are today, more than ever, highly aware of smile esthetics.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest

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